

KEY INDICATORS

With 190,947 hectares (2024), Switzerland had 18.4% of its farmland under organic management in 2024. While Switzerland is not a member state of the European Union, it had a considerably higher organic area share than the EU's average of 11.1%. Organic farmland more than doubled in the 2001 to 2024 period, thus growing at a considerably slower pace than in most other countries analyzed here. With 4,354.4 million euros, Switzerland had the fourth-largest market in Europe. 12.3 percent of all food sales were organic, the highest value worldwide.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)	93,955 ha (8.8%)	190,947 ha (18.4%)
Area Growth from 2001 to 2024	103.2%	

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)	1,711 ha (2.6%)	49,549 ha (12.4%)
Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)	868 ha (3.7%)	4,576 ha (19.1%)
Grassland* (Share of Total)	78,049 ha (4.4%)	133,752 ha (22.3%)
Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)	N/D	N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)	5441 (7.9%)	7,889 (16.8%)
Aquaculture Producers	N/D	N/D
Processors	N/D	1,144
Importers	N/D	791

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)	617 M€	4,354.4 M€ (12.3%)
Per Capita Consumption	86.1 €	480 €
Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024	345.1%	
Imports	N/D	N/D

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

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DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN SWITZERLAND

Source: Bio Suisse, Bundesamt für Statistik

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN SWITZERLAND

Source: Bio Suisse

ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

Switzerland is not a member of the European Union and does not participate in the Common Agricultural Policy, but it does have similar support mechanisms for conversion to and maintenance of organic farming, albeit at higher per ha values. Switzerland has no federal organic action plans, but some individual Cantons do. These were not analysed as part of this project. Aquaculture policy in Switzerland was not analysed as part of this project. Support for sustainable practices, e.g., non-use of pesticides, efficient nitrogen use or specific animal welfare measures, can be combined with the organic farming support indicated below.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	156 kha	N/D
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	14.9 %	N/D
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	97%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	156 M€	N/D
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	308 €	N/D

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (CHF/ha)	2019	200	1200	1600	1600	1600
	2023	200	1200	1600	1600	1600
Change from 2019 to 2023		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Maintenance Support (CHF/ha)	2019	200	1200	1600	1600	1600
	2023	200	1200	1600	1600	1600
Change from 2019 to 2023		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2023	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

CHF/EUR exchange rate ca. 1:1 in 2023, 1:1.1 in 2026

Sources for page 3

Lampkin N, Lembo G, Rehburg P (2024) Assessment of agricultural and aquaculture policy responses to the organic F2F targets. OrganicTargets4EU project Deliverable 1.2. Braunschweig: Thünen-Institut.

Sources for updates: Contacts in national Ministries and organic sector organisations (pers. comm. 2026)

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